

SYNTHESIS OF SUBSTITUTED DINITROPHENYLKETONES AND PHENYLACETIC ACIDS. PART V

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2:6-Dinitro-4-chlorophenyl-acetone and -acetic acid and 2-methyl-3-carbomethoxy-4-amino-6-chloroindole have been prepared.

The reaction described in previous communications (Sen and Bhargava, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 24, 268, 371; 1948, 25, 282, 403) has been extended to the preparation of 2:6-dinitro-4-chlorophenyl-acetone and -acetic acid, by the condensation of mono-sodium derivative of acetoacetic ester with 2:5-dichloro-1:3-dinitrobenzene and subsequent hydrolysis. Similar condensation with malonic ester yields 2:6-dinitro-4-chlorophenylmalonic ester. The reduction of 2:6-dinitro-4-chlorophenylacetoacetic ester results in the formation of an indole derivative.

EXPERIMENTAL

2:5-Dichloro-1-nitrobenzene and 2:5-Dichloro-1:3-dinitrobenzene.—The former was obtained by adding *p*-dichlorobenzene (20.8 g.) in small quantities, with stirring, to fuming nitric acid (*d* 1.52, 26 c.c.) cooled in ice-water. The product after standing at the room temperature for a short time, was poured into ice-water, and the solid that separated out was washed and dried, m.p. 54°, yield 27 g.

To obtain 2:5-dichloro-1:3-dinitrobenzene, 2:5-dichloro-1-nitrobenzene (27g.) was covered with sulphuric acid (conc., 90 c.c.), cooled in ice water, and treated with nitrating mixture (fuming nitric acid 28 c. c., *d*, 1.52 and fuming sulphuric acid 28 c.c., 26% SO₃) dropwise. When the addition of the nitrating mixture was complete, it was heated on a water-bath at 85° and stirred for 3 hours. The product was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature and poured over crushed ice; the precipitate was removed, washed and recrystallised from hot alcohol, yield 28 g.

2:6-Dinitro-4-chlorophenylacetoacetic Ester.—Acetoacetic ester (18 g.) was treated with sodium (3.2 g.) in anhydrous ether; after the last traces of sodium had disappeared, the flask was cooled in ice and 2:5-dichloro-1:3-dinitrobenzene (16 g.) was added. The mixture was stirred for 1½ hours in the cold and then refluxed for 6 hours with continued stirring. It was then extracted with 2% caustic soda solution (300 c. c.); the extract was cooled with ice and acidified with dilute nitric acid, when a red oil separated. This was allowed to settle, and left in a refrigerator overnight, when the greater part of the oil solidified. The supernatant aqueous layer was decanted off, the mixture was well shaken with 50 c. c. of alcohol and then filtered. The residue on the filter paper consisted of beautiful orange-red plates of 2:6-dinitro-4-chlorophenylacetoacetic ester. A further crop of the ester was obtained by allowing the filtrate to evaporate slowly, m.p. 81° yield 12.5 g. (56% of theory). (Found: N, 8.51. C₁₂H₁₁O₇N₂Cl requires N, 8.47 per cent).

2:6-Dinitro-4-chlorophenylacetone.—2:6-Dinitro-4-chlorophenylacetoacetic ester (4 g.) was dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid (50 c.c.), and water (25 c. c.) was then added to it without cooling, when a brisk evolution of CO_2 commenced. After this had ceased to evolve, the resulting black solution was poured on crushed ice, left in a refrigerator overnight and then filtered, when the crude ketone was obtained as a light brown powder. It was recrystallised by dissolving in hot alcohol, filtering and allowing the filtrate to evaporate by itself, when light brown needles of the ketone were obtained, m.p. $122-23^\circ$, yield theoretical. (Found: N, 10.99. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_6\text{N}_2\text{Cl}$ requires N, 10.83 per cent).

The *phenylhydrazone* of the above ketone was obtained by refluxing the crude ketone (1 g.), dissolved in a small quantity of alcohol, with phenylhydrazine (1 c. c.) for 45 minutes. The solution was then cooled in ice, diluted with a small quantity of water and filtered. The dark coloured residue was dissolved in hot alcohol, filtered and the filtrate allowed to evaporate by itself, when the phenylhydrazone crystallised out as dark brownish red needles, m.p. $117-18^\circ$ yield 0.8 g. (59.4% of theory). (Found: N, 16.28. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4\text{Cl}$ requires N, 16.06 per cent).

The *oxime* of the dinitrochlorophenylacetone was obtained by dissolving the ketone (1 g.) in hot alcohol, cooling, adding to it hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1.2 g.), followed by a drop of phenolphthalein and then caustic soda solution added drop by drop, till alkaline to phenolphthalein, and refluxing for three quarters of an hour. The greater part of the alcohol was then removed by distillation; the residue was cooled and then diluted with a small amount of water. The brown crystalline mass of the oxime that separated, was filtered off, dissolved in hot alcohol, filtered hot, and the filtrate allowed to evaporate by itself when very fine, light brown needles of the oxime were obtained, m.p. 111° , yield 1 g. (94.5% of theory). (Found: N, 15.36. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{O}_5\text{N}_2\text{Cl}$ requires N, 15.32 per cent).

2:6-Dinitro-4-chlorophenylacetic Acid.—2:6-Dinitro-4-chlorophenylacetoacetic ester (2 g.) was refluxed with 20% alcoholic potash (25 c.c.) and water (1.5 c. c.) for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours and the alcohol was then distilled off. The residue was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and the dark coloured crystalline mass that separated out, was filtered off. It was dissolved in alcohol, filtered, and the filtrate allowed to evaporate slowly. The dark brown crystals of the acid separating were further purified by dissolving in sodium carbonate solution, filtering and reprecipitating by hydrochloric acid, when the desired acid was obtained as a light brown powder. It does not melt, but decomposes on strong heating, yield 1 g. (63.4% of theory). (Found: N, 10.93. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_5\text{O}_6\text{N}_2\text{Cl}$ requires N, 10.75 per cent).

2-Methyl-3-carbethoxy-4-amino-6-chloroindole.—A mixture of 2:6-dinitro-4-chlorophenylacetoacetic ester (1.2 g.), iron powder (2.6 g.), crystallised ferrous sulphate (0.3 g.) and water (10 c. c.) was refluxed for 3 hours on a free but low flame. The mixture was then cooled with shaking in ice and filtered. The residue was extracted four times with 10 c. c. of alcohol each time, and the extract filtered hot. The filtrate which was first colorless, but turned dark violet in a very short time, was allowed to evaporate under cover, when the cyclised amine separated out as colorless crystals turning dark violet immediately on exposure to air. It begins to soften at 194° and

finally melts at 217° , yield 0.8 g. (87.3% of theory). (Found: N, 10.99. $C_{12}H_{13}O_2N_2Cl$ requires N, 11.09 per cent).

2:6-Dinitro-4-chlorophenylmalonic Ester.—The sodium derivative of malonic ester was obtained in the usual way from diethyl malonate (25 g.) and sodium (3.5 g.) in anhydrous ether (75 c. c.). When the last traces of sodium had disappeared, the flask was surrounded by ice and 2:5-dichloro-1:3-dinitrobenzene (12 g.) added. The mixture was stirred for one and a half hour in cold and then refluxed for 6 hours with continued stirring. It was then extracted with 2% caustic soda solution, the aqueous extract was cooled with ice, acidified with dilute nitric acid and left in a refrigerator overnight, when a red semi-solid mass settled down. The supernatant liquid was decanted off, the semi-solid mass dissolved in alcohol, the alcoholic solution filtered, and the filtrate allowed to evaporate slowly, when orange-red plates of the dinitrochlorophenylmalonic ester separated out, m.p. 85, yield 4 g. (22% of theory). (Found: N, 7.88. $C_{11}H_{13}O_8N_2Cl$ requires N, 7.79 per cent).

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